

International Peer Review Journal

ISSN 1817-5562

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine

The Official Journal of the Iraqi Ministry of Health

Volume 3 Number 3 December 2007

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

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www.newiraqijm.4t.com

Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index medicus

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Variation in the Lobes and Fissures of the Right Lung: An Anatomical Perspective

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Abstract

Background: The right lung is known to exhibit variations regarding the presence of fissures and lobes. Often the anomalies pertaining to the lungs remain undetected if they are asymptomatic. The variations may be detected incidentally in routine autopsies and cadaveric dissections.

Methods: We studied thirty five cadaveric right lungs (n=35) to detect any anomalies pertaining to fissures and lobes.

Results: Out of thirty five specimens studied, anomalous fissure and lobe was detected in a single lung specimen. The anomalous lung exhibited a single oblique fissure which did not extend to the inferior border, rather it extended to the anterior border of the right lung. The presence of the single oblique fissure resulted in formation of two lobes in the right lung.

Conclusion: Anatomical knowledge of the abnormal fissures and lobes of the lungs may be important for surgeons performing lobectomies. The presence of the anomalous lobes and fissures may also result in erroneous interpretation of skiagrams.

Keywords: Lung; Lobes; Anomaly; Variation; Anatomy.

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Introduction

According to standard anatomy textbook, the right lung has two fissures i.e. the oblique fissure and the horizontal fissure which divides it into three lobes: superior, middle and the inferior [1]. The oblique fissure (OF) can be traced, traversing a downward course thereby meeting the inferior border of the lung at a distance of 7.5 cm behind the anterior end [1]. The horizontal fissure (HF) passes from the OF at the level of the midaxillary line to the anterior border of

the lung at the level of the sternal end of the fourth costal cartilage. An OF, passing to the anterior border of the right lung, is a rare entity.

In the present study, we describe the gross anatomical features of an anomalous lung with an OF traversing a horizontal course to terminate at the anterior border of the right lung, thereby resulting in the formation of unusual two lobes instead of the usual two lobes. Anatomical knowledge of the normal and abnormal fissures and lobes of the lung may be important for surgeons and radiologists in day to day clinical practice and the present study is made to highlight such.

Materials and Methods

We observed thirty five right lungs (n=35) for the presence of anomalous fissures and lobes. No information regarding the history of the individuals were available. The right lungs were carefully studied, morphometric measurements were taken and the specimen was photographed (Fig.1). The anomalous specimen was also compared to a normal specimen (Fig.2).

Results

Out of thirty five specimens studied, we observed anomalous fissures and lobes in a single specimen (2.84%). The posterior border of the right lung was traced from above and a distance of 13 cm from the apex, an OF was traced to traverse a course towards the anterior border ('OF' in Fig.1). The OF on its origin from the posterior border was

prominent over a distance of 7 cm, thereby becoming faint while reaching the anterior border. The extent of the posterior border from the origin of the OF till the inferior border, measured 12.5 cm. There was only a single fissure i.e. the OF with the HF being absent. Only two lobes i.e. superior and the inferior, were observed in the present case.

Discussion

The anomalous fissures and the lobes may be due to defective development of the lungs. It has been reported that the fissures are the spaces which separate individual bronchopulmonary buds or segments and there is obliteration except along the two planes which give rise to the HF and the OF [2]. Whenever there is non obliteration of these spaces, the accessory fissure arises [2].

Many past research studies have focused on the accessory fissures. A past research study had reported an accessory fissure in the right lung between the superior and the basal segments of the lower lobes [3]. Studies performed by high resolution CT examinations on 30 healthy individuals found that in 87% and 77% cases, there were incomplete fissures in the right and the left lung, respectively [4]. Incompleteness of fissures (fusion between the lobes) has been reported to have 70% incidence [5]. A past study had even attempted to classify the pulmonary fissures [6]. The grades were classified as :- Grade 1- complete fissures, separate lobes; Grade 2- complete visceral cleft but parenchymal fissure at base of fissures; Grade 3- visceral cleft evident for part of the fissure; Grade 4- complete fusion of the lobes with no evidence of fissural

lobes. The same study had defined the pulmonary artery to be centrally located to the OF and termed the displacement of the artery in anterior and the posterior directions as ‘imbalance’

In CT scans, the major fissures may be visualized as lucent band, less often a line and least often as a dense band [7]. Localization of tumor or any mass in the lung along the fissures may be important. Often, the abnormal fissures may result in erroneous interpretation of skiagrams. It has been found that incomplete fissures often give an atypical appearance of the pleural effusion [8]. An incomplete major fissure has been identified to be linked to the spread of any disease and causing collateral drift [8]. Some radiologists have termed it as ‘incomplete fissure sign’ [8]. In the present case, the abnormal course of the OF will definitely cause an imaging conflict.

An incomplete fissure has been found to be the cause for post operative leakage [6]. It has been found also that accessory fissure acts as a barrier to the infection spread causing a sharply margined pneumonia which can be mistaken as atelectasis or consolidation [9]. An earlier anatomical study had defined the presence of an accessory fissure in the right lung with the presence of four lobes [10]. Thus, it is an accepted fact that the right lung may exhibit variations regarding the number of fissures and lobes.

Conclusion

Although, presence of two lobes and an accessory ‘azygos lobe’ in the right lung is not an uncommon finding as described in anatomy textbook [11], the awareness

of the same may be beneficial for surgeons performing lobectomies and radiologists interpreting skiagrams. The present anatomical finding is a sincere attempt to highlight such.

Figure legend

Fig.1. Photograph of anomalous right lung showing:

Ap:Apex ; **A:**Anterior border ; **C:**Costal surface; **OF:**Oblique fissure

Fig.2. Photograph of normal right and left lungs showing:

AP:Apex of lung ; **HF:**Horizontal fissure; **OF:**Oblique fissure; **RL:**Right lung; **Ao:**Arch of aorta; **Aph:**Apex of heart; **C:**Cardiac notch; **LL:**Left lung; **D:**Diaphragmatic surface

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